
Determination of Heavy Metals in Soil from Bokkos and Mangu Local Government Areas of Plateau State, Nigeria

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Abstract This study was conducted at Bokkos and Mangu local government areas of plateau state, Nigeria. Soil sample at varying depth(0 – 10 cm, 10 – 20 cm and 20 - 30 cm)were analyzed for heavy metals. This is to ascertain the effect of leaching in heavy metals concentration at various soil depths and to understand the phenomenon of heavy metals accumulation in plants. Soil samples were collected at six different locations (Batura, Mangor, Mbar, Kirang, Ampang and Bwai) in the two study areas. The samples were digested and analyzed for Cr, Ni, Cu, Mn, Fe, Zn and Pb Using standard procedures. The results showed high concentration of metals analyzed, with highest concentration of each metal as follows; Cr ($2.59 \pm 0.81 \mu\text{g/g}$); Ni ($3.60 \pm 0.81 \mu\text{g/g}$); Zn ($1.19 \pm 0.68 \mu\text{g/g}$); Cu ($1.92 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{g/g}$); Mn ($4.79 \pm 0.12 \mu\text{g/g}$); Fe ($52.27 \pm 2.81 \mu\text{g/g}$) and Pb ($0.45 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g/g}$). Among all the metals analyzed, Fe showed highest concentration while Pb showed the lowest concentration at all depth. The values obtained were observed to be statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. All values obtained were above the WHO permissible limit, therefore the soil of Bokkos and Mangu local government areas were found to be polluted at the time of this study which may lead to possible contamination of plant cultivated on them.

Keywords Heavy Metals, Soil, Mangu, Bokkos

Introduction

Environmental pollution related to industrialization and urbanization is inevitable unless proper measures are taken [1-2]. Pollution is one of the major problems around the world today in which thousands of millions of world inhabitants suffer health problems related to industry and atmospheric pollutants [3]. Recent years have witnessed significant attention being paid to the problems of environmental contamination by wide variety of chemical pollutants including heavy metals [4]. Soil has been recognized as the major sink for anthropogenic heavy metal deposition through various pathways [5-6]. The contamination of soil by heavy metals can be problematic on several levels because they do not degrade biologically [7] and this always result in several soil dysfunctions leading to concerns about the environmental quality. Metal contaminated soil poses risks to humans and animals through ingestion of plants that have bio-accumulated toxic metals from contaminated soil [8]. In most soil environment sorption is the dominating speciation process and thus the largest fraction of heavy metal in a soil is associated with the solid phase of that soil [9]. Pollution problem arise when heavy metals are mobilized into the soil solution and taken up by plants or transported to the surface/ground water. The properties of the soil are thus very important in the attenuation of heavy metals in the environment. The solubility of heavy metals in soil is controlled by reactions with solid phases [10]. Once sewage sludge is applied to soil, the heavy metal species undergo several possible fates. The environmental problems with heavy metals are that they as elements are undestroyable and that most of them have toxic effects on living organisms when exceeding a certain concentration [8]. Furthermore, some heavy metals are being subjected to bioaccumulation and may pose a risk to human health when transferred to the food chain. The adverse effect of heavy metals is inseparably related to the soil's ability to adsorb and retain sub elements [11]. The pH of the soil play a great role in mobility of these metals in soil. Solution maintained at neutral to slightly alkaline condition showed low

mobility of all heavy metals. To increase the mobility of heavy metals, the pH of the soil solution should be lowered. Indiscriminate anthropogenic activities such as mining on Jos Plateau leads to many part of areas being exposed to erosion and reduced available arable land for crop production. Toxic metals bio-accumulate in the body via the food chain. Toxic heavy metals may affect germination, young or old trees stem growth, leaf formation, root growth, flowering, fruiting, plant growth rate and biomes photosynthesis, transpiration, mineral nutrition and secondary metabolism. Chemicals come and go but rarely disappear completely from our ecosystem [12].

Materials and Methods

Study location

Bokkos local government area is located in central part of Plateau state, it headquarters is in the town of Bokkos. It is located at 9°18'00" N / 9°00'00" E. It has a total area of 1,682 km² (649 square miles) and a population of 178,454 at 2006 census (NPC, 2006). The people there are mostly farmers and they are also involves in mining of tin locally. The language spoken by most people in Bokkos local government is Ron.

Mangu (Mongu) local government area is located in central part of Plateau state, Nigeria. Its headquarters is located in the town of Mangu. It lies at 9° 31' 00" N / 9° 06' 00" E. It has a total area of 1,653 km² and a population of 294,931 at 2006 census (NPC, 2006). Languages spoken are mostly Mwaghavul and Pyem. Their occupation is mostly farming and local tin mining. The two local government are, bordered by Barikin Ladi, Pankshin and Qua'anpan .

Sample collection

Soil at varying depth (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm, and 20-30 cm), were collected from three locations, Mangor, Nbar and Batura in Bokos Local Government Area. Kirang, Ampang and Bwai in Mangu local government area with a control farm few meters from the sample area which has less Agricultural activities to serve as control sample, all in Plateau state, Nigeria. Each sample was labeled with a unique identification number at each sample area. The sample was collected monthly for the period of three months.

Table 1: Mean concentration of heavy metals in µg/g in soil samples at varying depth from Mangor study area, Bokkos LGA, Plateau State

Depth	Cr	Ni	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	Pb
0-10cm	0.63 ^a ±0.16	1.47 ^a ±0.67	0.12 ^a ±0.02	0.44 ^a ±0.15	3.20 ^a ±1.35	13.98 ^a ±0.59	0.11 ^a ±0.20
10-20cm	0.68 ^b ±0.07	1.55 ^b ±0.12	0.17 ^b ±0.04	0.53 ^b ±0.18	3.37 ^b ±1.07	38.16 ^b ±1.51	0.37 ^b ±0.26
20-30cm	1.73 ^c ±0.83	2.92 ^c ±0.45	0.21 ^c ±0.10	1.92 ^c ±1.03	3.42 ^c ±1.20	49.36 ^c ±1.67	0.45 ^c ±0.16
Control							
0-10cm	0.02 ±0.02	0.05 ^a ± 0.05	0.06 ^a ±0.01	0.06 ^a ± 0.04	0.13 ^a ± 0.02	1.20 ^a ± 0.11	0.06 ^a ±0.02
10-20cm	0.05 ^b ±0.01	0.19 ^b ±1.03	0.09 ^b ±0.03	0.08 *±0.01	0.39*± 0.07	3.11 ^b ± 0.14	0.12 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.09*±0.04	0.21 ^c ±0.11	1.04 ±0.08	0.13 ^c ±0.02	0.81 ^c ± 0.51	5.60 ^c ±1.08	0.17*±0.06
Standard	0.3	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1

Values presented are mean ± SD of replicate date. Within column, paired mean with different alphabets are statistically significant (p<0.05). Key: SD = Standard Deviation, * = not significant

Cr = Chromium, Ni = Nickel, Zn = Zinc, Cu = Copper, Mn = Manganese, Fe= Iron, Pb = Lead

Table 2: Mean concentration of heavy metals in µg/g in soil samples at varying depth from Mbar study area, Bokkos LGA, Plateau State.

Depth	Cr	Ni	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	Pb
0-10cm	0.35 ^a ±0.56	1.22 ^a ±0.17	0.14 ^a ±0.36	0.34 ^a ±0.25	0.93 ^a ±0.58	22.85 ^a ±2.48	0.29 ^a ±0.06
10-20cm	0.38 ^b ±0.44	1.36 ^b ±0.31	0.37 ^b ±0.04	0.92 ^b ±0.52	2.59 ^b ±1.75	25.33 ^b ±1.05	0.34 ^b ±0.03
20-30cm	0.49*±0.51	1.48 ^c ±0.39	0.39 ^c ±0.30	0.98 ^c ±0.31	2.94 ^c ±1.71	52.27 ^c ±2.81	0.37 ^c ±0.05
Control							
0-10cm	0.02 ±0.02	0.05 ^a ± 0.05	0.06 ^a ±0.01	0.06 ^a ± 0.04	0.13 ^a ± 0.02	1.20 ^a ± 0.11	0.06 ^a ±0.02
10-20cm	0.05 ^b ±0.01	0.19 ^b ±1.03	0.09 ^b ±0.03	0.08 *±0.01	0.39*± 0.07	3.11 ^b ± 0.14	0.12 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.09*±0.04	0.21 ^c ±0.11	1.04 ±0.08	0.13 ^c ±0.02	0.81 ^c ± 0.51	5.60 ^c ±1.08	0.17*±0.06
Standard	0.3	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1

Values presented are mean ± SD of replicate date. Within column, paired mean with different alphabets are statistically significant (p<0.05). Key: SD = Standard Deviation, * = not significant

Cr = Chromium, Ni = Nickel, Zn = Zinc, Cu = Copper, Mn= Manganese, Fe= Iron, Pb = Lead

Table 3: Mean concentration of heavy metals in $\mu\text{g/g}$ in soil samples at varying dept from Batura study area, Bokkos LGA, Plateau State.

Depth	Cr	Ni	Zn	Cu	Mn	Pb	Fe
0-10cm	0.32 ^a ±0.09	1.08 ^a ±0.01	0.81 ^a ±0.53	0.90 ^a ±0.43	4.30 ^a ±0.19	12.40 ^a ±0.55	0.22 ^a ±0.02
10-20cm	0.39 ^b ±0.01	1.09 ^b ±0.02	1.04 ^b ±0.81	1.04 ^b ±0.66	4.70 ^b ±0.41	14.55 ^b ±1.31	0.23 ^b ±0.02
20-30cm	0.46 ^c ±0.05	1.15 ^c ±0.11	1.05 ^c ±0.60	1.53 [*] ±0.79	4.73 ^c ±0.12	16.67 ^c ±1.30	0.30 ^c ±0.09
Control							
0-10cm	0.02 ±0.02	0.05 ^a ± 0.05	0.06 ^a ±0.01	0.06 ^a ± 0.04	0.13 ^a ± 0.02	1.20 ^a ± 0.11	0.06 ^a ±0.02
10-20cm	0.05 ^b ±0.01	0.19 ^b ±1.03	0.09 ^b ±0.03	0.08 [*] ±0.01	0.39 [*] ± 0.07	3.11 ^b ± 0.14	0.12 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.09 [*] ±0.04	0.21 ^c ±0.11	1.04 ±0.08	0.13 ^c ±0.02	0.81 ^c ± 0.51	5.60 ^c ±1.08	0.17 [*] ±0.06
Standard	0.3	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1

Values presented are mean \pm SD of replicate date. Within column, paired mean with different alphabets are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Key: SD = Standard Deviation, * = not significant

Cr = Chromium, Ni = Nickel, Zn = Zinc, Cu = Copper, Mn= Manganese, Fe= Iron, Pb = Lead

Table 4: Mean concentration of heavy metals in $\mu\text{g/g}$ in soil samples at varying depth from Kirang study area, Mangu LGA, Plateau state, Nigeria.

Depth	Cr	Ni	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	Pb
0-10cm	0.88 ^a ±0.17	1.15 ^a ± 0.05	0.20 ^a ±0.06	0.29 ^a ±0.33	2.01 ^a ± 0.96	18.17 ^a ±1.78	0.22 [*] ±0.04
10-20cm	1.36 ^b ±0.89	2.14 [*] ± 0.10	0.23 ^b ± 0.04	0.23 ^b ±0.07	2.05 ^b ± 1.08	27.08 ^b ± 2.23	0.23 [*] ±0.05
20-30cm	2.59 ^c ± 0.72	2.20 ^c ± 0.09	0.37 ^c ±0.11	0.42 ^c ±0.07	2.61 ^c ± 0.47	42.78 ^c ±2.75	0.27 ^c ±0.05
Control							
0-10cm	0.02 ±0.02	0.05 ^a ±0.05	0.06 ^a ±0.01	0.06 ^a ±0.04	0.13 ^a ±0.02	1.20 ^a ±0.11	0.06 ^a ±0.02
10-20cm	0.05 ^b ±0.01	0.19 ^b ±1.03	0.09 ^b ±0.03	0.08 [*] ±0.01	0.39 [*] ±0.07	3.11 ^b ±0.14	0.12 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.09 [*] ±0.04	0.21 ^c ±0.11	1.04 ^c ±0.08	0.13 ^c ±0.02	0.81 ^c ±0.51	5.60 ^c ± 1.08	0.17 [*] ±0.06
Standard	0.3	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1

Values presented are mean \pm SD. replicate data within column, paired mean with different alphabets are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Key: SD = Standard Deviation, * = not significant

Cr = Chromium, Ni = Nickel, Zn = Zinc, Cu = Copper, Mn= Manganese, Fe= Iron, Pb = Lead

Table 5: Mean concentration of heavy metals in $\mu\text{g/g}$ in soil samples at varying depth from Ampang study area, Mangu LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Depth	Cr	Ni	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	Pb
0-10cm	0.21 ^a ±0.08	0.22 [*] ±0.03	0.18 ^a ±0.08	0.10 ^a ±1.39	1.04 ^a ±0.06	5.34 ^a ±3.03	0.26 ^a ±0.07
10-20cm	0.11 ^b ±0.03	1.43 [*] ±0.04	0.19 ^b ±0.06	0.13 ^b ±1.46	1.09 ^b ±0.15	16.44 ^b ±2.18	0.20 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.30 ^c ± 0.30	1.46 [*] ±0.03	0.21 ^c ±0.04	1.15 ^c ±1.41	1.33 ^c ±0.29	17.58 ^c ±3.44	0.19 ^c ±0.10
Control							
0-10cm	0.02 ±0.02	0.05 ^a ±0.05	0.06 ^a ±0.01	0.06 ^a ±0.04	0.13 ^a ±0.02	1.20 ^a ±0.11	0.06 ^a ±0.02
10-20cm	0.05 ^b ±0.01	0.19 ^b ±1.03	0.09 ^b ±0.03	0.08 [*] ±0.01	0.39 [*] ±0.07	3.11 ^b ±0.14	0.12 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.09 [*] ±0.04	0.21 ^c ±0.11	1.04±0.08	0.13 ^c ±0.02	0.81 ^c ±0.51	5.60 ^c ±1.08	0.17 [*] ±0.06
Standard	0.3	0.02	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.1

Values presented are mean \pm SD. replicate data within column, paired mean with different alphabets are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Key: SD = Standard Deviation, * = not significant

Cr = Chromium, Ni = Nickel, Zn = Zinc, Cu = Copper, Mn= Manganese, Fe= Iron, Pb = Lead

Table 6: Mean concentration of heavy metals in $\mu\text{g/g}$ in soil samples at varying depth from Bwai study area, Mangu LGA, Plateau State, Nigeria.

Depth	Cr	Ni	Zn	Cu	Mn	Fe	Pb
0-10cm	0.24 ^a ±0.26	1.28 ^a ±0.56	0.60 ^a ±0.76	0.27 ^a ±0.42	2.55 ^a ±1.32	11.40 ^a ± 1.50	0.36 ^a ±0.05
10-20cm	0.32 ^b ±0.39	2.39 ^b ±1.30	0.74 ^b ±0.72	0.67 [*] ±0.05	2.39 [*] ±1.11	14.74 ^b ± 0.70	0.42 ^b ±0.30
20-30cm	0.11 [*] ±0.22	3.60 ^c ±0.81	1.19 ^c ± 0.68	0.43 ^c ±0.54	2.68 ^c ±1.54	19.60 ^c ±1.82	0.27 [*] ±0.04
Control							
0-10cm	0.02 ±0.02	0.05 ^a ±0.05	0.06 ^a ±0.01	0.06 ^a ±0.04	0.13 ^a ±0.02	1.20 ^a ±0.11	0.06 ^a ±0.02

10-20cm	0.05 ^b ±0.01	0.19 ^b ±1.03	0.09 ^b ±0.03	0.08*±0.01	0.39*±0.07	3.11 ^b ±0.14	0.12 ^b ±0.01
20-30cm	0.09*±0.04	0.21 ^c ±0.11	1.04 ^c ±0.08	0.13 ^c ±0.02	0.81 ^c ±0.51	5.60 ^c ±1.08	0.17*±0.06
Standard	0.3	0.02	0.1	0.	0.3	0.1	0.1

Values presented are mean ± SD. replicate data within column, paired mean with different alphabets are statistically significant (p<0.05). Key: SD = Standard Deviation, * = not significant

Cr = Chromium, Ni = Nickel, Zn = Zinc, Cu = Copper, Mn = Manganese, Fe = Iron, Pb = Le

Sample Preparation

Two grams of soil sample was weighed into acid washed glass beaker and was digested by the addition of 20 cm³ of aqua regia, 10 cm³ of H₂O₂ was added in small portions to avoid any possible overflow leading to loss of materials from the beaker. The beaker was placed on hot plate and heated at 90 °C for two hours. The sample was filtered out to separate the insoluble solid from the supernatant liquid. The volume was adjusted to 100 cm³ with distilled water. The analysis was carried out using Perkin- Elmer Analyst 300 Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS).

Data collected was analyzed using (GraphPad InStat 2000). One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Turkey-Kramer's Multiple Comparison was used to assess the variation in concentration of heavy metals, cations and anions exchange capacity among the varieties. Possibilities less than (p<0.05) was considered statistically significant. Results were express as mean ± standard deviation

Discussion

This study revealed that, the Concentration of heavy metal in soil samples varies as the depth increase in the order 0-10cm < 10 – 20cm < 20 – 30 cm. It was observed that the concentration of iron in the study areas increases as the depth of the soil increases, which could be due to leaching. This result is in line with earlier reported work [13]. Due their bioavailability in soil plants tend to absorbed them because they need them for their normal metabolism. Heavy metals are present in food in very minute quantities; their existence is due to their role in the body metabolism. It has been established that whatever is taken as food might cause metabolic disturbance if it does not contain the permissible upper and lower limit of heavy metals. Thus the deficiency and excess of heavy metals (Iron, Zinc and chromium) may produce undesirable effect [14]. Effect of toxic metals on human health and their interaction with essential heavy metals may produce serious consequences [15]. It was observed by Uwah *et al.*, (2007); Akan *et al.*, (2013) [13, 16]. This study showed that, iron (Fe) showed the highest concentration in µg/g at all depths. The highest concentration of iron in all the soil of the study area was observed in Mbar study area at the depth 20–30 cm. It was also observed that Batura study area had the lowest concentration of iron.

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